

TITLE: Recognizing and reviving the legacy of Cavite's cuisines: Basis for promotion

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ABSTRACT

The study seeks to revive the selected four (4) of Cavite's cuisine, determining the familiarity level of the readers to achieve making it as a way to promote the included cuisines, such as Digman halo-halo, Imus longganisa, Bacalao, and Pipian. The researchers used descriptive questionnaires to gain information that strengthened the foundation of research objectives, such as effectively promoting the included Cavite's cuisines and the significance of conducting the study- which acquires the information of: (1)The legacy of Cavite in terms of its cuisines, (2)Awareness level of people on the areas of- specifically that this study focuses on the residences of Bacoor, Imus, and Dasmariñas in regards with the mentioned 4 Cavite's cuisines. (3)Achieving the goal of recognizing and reviving these cuisines in Cavite as the study focuses on establishing information about Digman halo-halo, Imus longganisa, Bacalao and Pipian.

Keywords: Cavite's cuisine, Familiarity level, Promoting, Awareness level, Recognizing, Reviving

INTRODUCTION

The study includes the cuisines in the province of Cavite, specifically the Digman Halo-halo, Imus Longganisa, Bacalao and Pipian. The study seeks the involved cuisines to be revived and recognized by determining the familiarity level within the location. Cavite is known as the 'History capital of the Philippines' for its rich history regarding destinations, heroes, and food. One of the famous cuisines in Cavite is Digman halo-halo, specifically at Bacoor- it is a popular dessert that is known as a creamy dessert with plenty of ingredients, consisting of milk, sugar, crushed ice, nata de coco, macapuno, monggo beans, and gulaman, topped with leche flan and ube ice cream. Digman halo-halo started in 1969 and has gained popularity, and it was even featured by two of the most known mass media entertainment: ABS-CBN and GMA. Imus Longganisa, a popular 'Filipino sausage' that is known as a product from Imus, Cavite. It is made from 100% meat, such as ground pork, with mixed soy sauce, black pepper, vinegar, and annatto- a condiment from the seed of achiote tree used as a food coloring (red-orange). There is also Bacalao in Cavite- one of the proud recipes of Caviteño. This dried fish could be mixed with different dishes in combination of vegetables, tomato paste, etc. Bacalao originated from the word 'Bacalhau', a dried codfish from Portugal and Brazil. This food is usually prepared in the Lenten season. Lastly, the

Pipian- is one of the cuisines in Cavite that originated from Spanish. It is similar to the famous Filipino food 'Kare-kare' but is a version with Chicken as the main ingredient instead of beef.

According to M.G Hernandez (2018), Preservation of traditional foods is also recommended that recipes should be kept and treasured because the recipes of the family hold memories of special foods and occasions that were once shared and celebrated with family members. Legacy of food is recommended that recording thoughts and ideas be more frequent because this creates an heirloom or an inheritance that must be handed down to future generations.

Food is necessary for every individual; it somehow connects a person to something or someone, whether inside, at home, or outside. The thought of preserving the legacy of mentioned foods in the study starts with recognizing and reviving its existence- determining how familiar the residents are with the four mentioned cuisines and how their presence can be increased, considering the developments and changes of time, preferences, curiosity, and knowledge.

According to N.G Baah (2020), this study explores how food-related personality traits of tourists influence attitudes. The study provides insights into the role of neophilia in explaining tourists' cognitive, affective, and cognitive responses toward local cuisines. Neophilia talks about a person's attitude: enthusiasm and love for what is new. The idea of the study is how this connects to how a specific person, as a potential customer, responds toward cuisines. The creativity being presented on a particular dish also impacts a customer's perception to consider a cuisine as a quality food.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The researcher believes that the results of the study will be necessary to students- The research aims to teach students about recognizing and reviving the legacy of Cavite's cuisines: Basis for promotion. The study may be an intellectual help by providing at least four cuisines of Cavite, with the location and description details, and how it will be presented and promoted- considering that multiple foods are a legacy to a specific location; Teachers- The outcome of this study may respond to the needs of the students when it comes to their academic performance. One example is in a class of the Hospitality Management Program wherein there are food-related subjects. The study could provide food-related topics and knowledge about cuisines being offered and available in Cavite, specifically, the four of Cavite's cuisines: the Digmaan halo-halo, Imus longganisa, Bacalao, and Pipian; The province of Cavite- The study attempts to be informative about the four included foods that are a legacy in Cavite in which it may: introduce the traditional food aspects, revive the four of the mentioned cuisines which it may strengthen the foundation of basis of the popular title of Cavite, "History capital of the Philippines" in reason that, Cavite is rich with history including from the subject of destinations, heroes, and foods; To Future Researchers- The study will help them in further research on recognizing and reviving the legacy of Cavite's cuisines: Basis for promotion establishes information with involvement on: (1) considering factors of what affects the decision making of an individual when trying a food/cuisine, (2) how familiar are the participants on mentioned cuisines- in which both are a basis on recognizing, reviving and promoting the subjects included and to the subject matter of preserving the legacy of Cavite's cuisines.

SCOPE AND DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The researchers intended to establish information about recognizing and reviving the legacy of Cavite's cuisines: Basis for promotion. The researchers included 100 random respondents, and the data gathering was conducted online among the residents of Bacoor, Imus, and Dasmarias from May 2022 - June 2023, using survey questionnaires in online form. The respondents were selected using random major sampling.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aims at recognizing and reviving the legacy of Cavite's cuisines: Basis for promotion specifically, the study seeks the answer to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?
 - 1.1 Age

- 1.2 Gender
- 1.3 Occupation
- 1.4 Location
2. How can the legacy cuisines of Cavite be effectively promoted?
 - 2.1 Preferences
 - 2.2 Cuisine background
3. What is the significance of the study?
 - 3.1 Familiarity

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to G. Migliore (2015), the quality of a food product should reflect the level of satisfaction the consumer derives from it (Cardello, 1995, Moskowitz, 1995). This depends on to what extent the product's characteristics meet consumer preferences.

Quality sets great customer satisfaction when purchasing, which relates to trying or ordering a cuisine in this study. Seeing great quality based on reviews boosts a customer's positive decision-making regarding trying or ordering. It is a standard that served quality must meet the consumer/customer's preferences for them to come back to a specific restaurant and business: the food industry. This is a bridge to reach a customer's high level of satisfaction that eventually may lead to them- trying a restaurant and ordering the cuisine again.

As stated by S. Oktay (2018), Every country has adopted a different food culture from a neighboring society. It has taken the food culture from those who migrated from faraway countries. Food culture in the Philippines has a significant impact in terms of businesses, especially offering products with rice (mainly white rice), which is considered the ultimate staple of Filipino food.

Rice is always expectedly present in every household and is more than likely part of every Filipino's meal from breakfast, lunch, and dinner. It is because rice always satisfies food cravings and, most especially, resolves hunger on a tiring day of a person as rice is known to consist of its plain, starchy flavor. It pairs well with many local and international dishes regardless of their original flavor, like sweetness, salty dishes, sour, bitter, smokey, and spicy. Aside from that, rice also plays a huge part in providing income or financial help to Filipino families, especially the farmers who work day and night to provide food to their own and to all the people dependent on rice to sustain the day-to-day nutrient needs. Therefore, Filipinos became rice eaters because it has been part of their culture and history. It became a norm for early Filipinos and passed down from generation to generation. It is called 'staple food' by most Filipinos because it is paired with different viands, even noodles and pasta. Now, it is introduced like Japanese-inspired cuisine partnered with rice with toppings of shrimp or pork, beef, chicken, mango, and many more, wrapped with tasty seaweed and rolled together- this cuisine is popularly known as Sushi.

According to M. Jehka (2021), This study identifies the relationship between food quality, price, and service quality with factors influencing visitors' purchase intention towards Kelantan cuisine. This research aims to help small and midsize food enterprises identify factors influencing visitors' purchase intention toward Kelantan cuisine.

It will always be important to be aware of the basic and simple details of a certain cuisine, knowing what ingredients a certain cuisine consists of and familiarizing with the aspects involved like its accessibility, quality based on feedback, a price that may be seen online and personal, food appearance and many more to ensure that the value is being seen like costing and pricing. Not only to be knowledgeable about the food but also about the food industry, precisely the field of business.

As stated by R. Liba (2017), the performance and internship performance of HM Students in Asian and Western Cuisine specifically determined the academic performance in Asian and Western Cuisine subjects; assessed the internship Performance in knowledge, skills, attitude, and Personality.

Philippine cuisine has been popularized today, and many countries have been replanting the local dish despite how tastier and more flavorful local cuisine is compared to others. Many tourists outside the country are trying to have a little taste of the local cuisine here in the Philippines. In the food industry, businesses, and future interns, it is expected to know even the tiny details of cuisine. R. Liba mentioned these internships wherein it is mentioned about knowledge, skills, and attitude. Internships measure and enhance the study's capabilities: the researcher's insightfulness and perception to attain the goal of recognizing, reviving, and promoting. Developing and enhancing capabilities when it comes to our local cuisine is much more helpful than learning any different kind of cuisine, making our local cuisine to be popular to some of the countries are inexperienced in originating their cuisine that's why some of the locals in their country are trying different variety of cuisine especially here in the Philippines many tourists are aggravating to taste the food compare to them because Filipinos preserve the quality and taste of local cuisine. With the help of education, they develop and make peculiar cuisine to maintain its flavor and taste, so many locals and tourists will be complacent to relish Filipino cuisine.

Based on the statement of M. Matsuishi (2021), Japan displays particularly advantageous geographical environment and climate conditions for abundant sea- and land-based food production. In 2013, traditional Japanese cuisine, i.e., Washoku, was registered as an Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity (UNESCO, 2013). Its characteristics comprise the variety and freshness of the ingredients.

The article mentioned the freshness of ingredients in which the mentioned cuisines are prepared with good quality ingredients, which is expected as this is a food industry. Exploring the cuisines also involves what is being included in the dishes that are being served to customers. Included as well is being aware of the cuisine background as sometimes, it happens that there are a lot of questions from the buyer, and it is only correct that all are being answered as a worker who attempts to achieve great customer service.

According to V. Tharavath (2017), the study reveals that these factors influence the preference for cuisines differently. For example, the personality of an individual has a significant influence over the preference of Indian and Arabic cuisines, while people who give more importance to the quality of food while eating out are more likely to prefer Indian cuisine.

The subject of influence is considered when a customer tries a particular cuisine. It could be influenced by peers or any related individuals that affect a person's decision-making in terms of trying a restaurant and ordering a cuisine. Furthermore, quality is still mentioned that regardless of the background or reason why a customer tries a particular restaurant and particular cuisine, the quality of food still has a major role in why a customer purchases.

Based on the statement of Dr. M. Gupta (2019), Introduction The format of home delivery or the takeaways have gained plenty of additional customers in locations like malls, offices, and big-party orders for residential complexes.

One of the modern generation's developments is that food businesses, specifically restaurants, have adapted to online access. Nowadays, people use the internet and spend most of their time on it. The reason is not only because this has become easy to use but because it has been convenient for people, through the help of online applications such as FoodPanda, Grab, etc.- which are the easiest and most convenient ways where customers could try the best selling cuisines without having to leave their home or workplaces. The online application contains images of products and small details about each menu input in the devices.

These applications are also a way to make the mentioned cuisines to be more known as the applications are available when it comes to inputting feedback about a particular restaurant. Facebook application is also being used for presenting cuisines, such as creating business pages on Facebook and posting cooking images in the application.

Based on L. Cañet (2021), they added that social media promotes a consumer to consumer approach, with consumers sharing their experiences and creating a common knowledge of servicing a product.

In promoting the cuisines involved in the study, social media platforms may play a stepping stone to accomplishing the goal of advertising. Internet and online applications are a majority of the most accessible tools to connect with different people, which could mean that posting information about the mentioned foods/cuisines online might come up to a large number of people, establishing knowledge of one's personal experience relating to the foods/cuisines involved in the study and passing each detail unintentionally or intentionally through another form of communication.

According to J. Levitt (2017), food tourism is an activity that has grown in popularity. While it encompasses different activities, consuming local cuisine appears to be particularly popular.

Food tourism is now widespread in our generation; sometimes, it is the job of an individual to visit different food businesses and give feedback about the offered products. Recognizing, reviving, and promoting the mentioned foods/cuisines are a part of what is continuously developing and captivates many people. Where a cuisine originates is also influential, especially when the country is known or popular. Ancestors influence the cuisines/foods, and some originated from other countries like the Pipian, which originated from Spanish, and Bacalao, which originated from Portugal and Brazil. Foods somehow exist with a history that is captivating and interesting to others.

According to T. Tawami (2019), the chances of Japanese food in Indonesia are very large. And making a Japanese business restaurant in Indonesia with a different menu variety would be advantageous. In addition, special food can become the Pull of a country to attract foreign tourists.

The cuisines/foods included in the study, some of the subjects are food originating from Spanish, Mexican, Portugal, and Brazil. This background may gain people's interest, which may affect the issue of trying a cuisine that connects to preserving its methods. This possibility involves the introduction of mentioned cuisines that originated outside the country. With this, people who travel or stay in the Philippines, whether foreign or local, won't be necessary to even go to a particular country just to see the beauty of the differences in the cuisines. This will be something new for food lovers, including residents and non-residents who are fed up with common local foods that are always available and can be seen anywhere.

As stated by R. Fanelli (2018), With the increase of tourism and international trade, the role of ethnicity in the world has become more important not only in business and consumer behavior but also in food culture and the food industry.

Culture significantly impacts the food industry by capturing a certain person, especially the potential consumer. Like the origin of Halo-halo, Longganisa, Bacalao, and Pipian, the mentioned dishes are a part of the trademark or culture in a particular location, such as the Philippines, Spanish, Portugal, and Brazil. While exploring these dishes, many other people also try to introduce themselves through these dishes. Some are even traveling from far away just to see the beauty of that specific dish. It has influenced many businesses and residents and is currently offering foods that originate internationally and locally. For

example, the Pipian is a legacy cuisine that is served with rice, which is always perfect as rice is a staple food in the Philippines.

According to D. Chakraborty (2021), online food ordering apps (OFOAs) have become increasingly popular, and consumers have widely recognized their benefits, particularly during pandemics or lockdowns. Despite the growing popularity of OFOAs, little is known about technology acceptance theories and their impact on purchase intention. The current study proposes amalgamating three theories to bridge this gap, better explaining customer behavior toward OFOAs.

Promoting could come with a tool of making the cuisines available for purchasing online or online access, expanding the number of consumers by posting the food on social media platforms and food-related applications. Online opportunities included consumers ordering meals that made it convenient for them and accessible as they no longer needed to go or buy their meals at restaurants. As hospitality management students, social media or online access also helps introduce particular food. Access to the Internet also impacts the influence of food in the Philippines. The Internet has been a continuous path to connect from far away locations that may involve eye openers to different traditional aspects related to food in this study. Now, regarding food being offered, all are continuously evolving, and online platforms are a way to introduce these changes.

METHODOLOGY

Presents the methods and techniques of the study, the research design, the population of the study, and the data-gathering procedure, including the scaling system. The study included four cuisines in Cavite that were selected to narrow the subjects by location.

Research design

This study utilized the descriptive research design to describe the data being studied: recognizing and reviving the legacy of Cavite's cuisines: Basis for promotion. It aims to obtain information that accurately answers the concern involved in the study.

Methods and technique of the study

Three research questions were addressed in this study. An overview of the population, random sampling, sample size, and data collection method as research design were presented, and the development of the survey instrument and validity and reliability of the instrument were explained. Finally, data analysis techniques will be given- proposed conceptual model on determinants of residents' perceived advantage is to be developed to examine and answer the research questions as follows: Q1: the preferences of participants that affect decision-making regarding trying a cuisine, Q2: familiarity level, Q3: Significance of the study This chapter addresses a research framework and two research questions. Further, data collection methods and research design will be presented. The development of the survey instrument, validity, and reliability of the instrument will be explained, and finally, data analysis techniques will be presented. The results are to be presented in the following chapter.

Population of the Study The researchers of this study included the location of Imus, Bacoor and Dasmariñas. Random sampling was used in selection making, specifically including students, residents, and non-residents and teachers or workers that would benefit the mentioned profile of respondents. Recognizing and reviving the legacy of Cavite's cuisines is beneficial for Students- gaining knowledge about the legacy cuisines of Cavite, which they may be able to use for academic purposes. Residents and non-residents for additional ideas on where they can try cuisines in Cavite. Teachers/workers- included in

providing additional information that they can use for academic purposes or engaging in conversation with others.

Research Instrument

The data gathering included surveys, specifically answering the questionnaires that were held online and face-to-face. The data collection establishes answers regarding what cuisines are presented in Cavite and what are the reasons participants when trying and ordering a cuisine in which all are included in the topic: recognizing and reviving the legacy of Cavite's cuisines: Basis for promotion.

Data collection and data analysis procedure

Survey questionnaires are given online. Online surveys were done through an online form and distributed to consumers/participants inside the location intended: Imus, Bacoor, and Dasmaringas. The data gathered are presented using tables with accurate interpretation. The survey questionnaires were pilot tested and given to 15 respondents, and final surveys were computed using the Cronbach statistical method.

RESULTS

Table 1: Presents data that establishes the reasons of the respondents when trying a cuisine.

No.	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	Price and quality are a factor when trying a cuisine, in addition that- It is more likely that a consumer tries a cuisine based on food appearance and trend/popularity. In terms of: Familiarity and accessibility to the cuisines affects decision making of the respondents when trying or visiting.	4.06	Agree

The table shows that in terms of trying a cuisine, there are particular factors and aspects that the study includes: price, quality, familiarity, appearance, trend, and accessibility- which affect the decision-making of a potential consumer. Based on the data gathered regarding the six mentioned factors, most respondents agree with them. Consumers view a cuisine's price and quality, along with trends, food appearance, and accessibility. Potential customers tend to try a particular cuisine when there is familiarity with what is being explicitly presented, familiarity in terms of how aware the consumers are about the food: its place of availability and accessibility or the history or background.

Figure 1: Presents data that determines the level of familiarity of the participants regarding the mentioned cuisines such as: Digman halo-halo, Imus longganisa, Bacalao and Pipian.

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Digman halo-halo	66	36%
Imus longganisa	63	35%
Bacalao	25	14%
Pipian	27	15%

Data shows Digman Halo-halo is the most heard cuisine/food among the four legacy cuisines, followed by Imus longganisa with a total percentage of 35. 14% of the respondents have heard of Bacalao, and finally,

the cuisine with the lowest percentage is Pipian.

Figure 2: Participants NEVER have heard the following cuisines

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Digman halo-halo	24	16%
Imus longganisa	17	11%
Bacalao	56	36%
Pipian	53	35%

Based on the data gathered, the cuisine that has yet to be heard from the respondents is Bacalao, with a percentage of 36, followed by Pipian, with a total percentage of 35. Imus longganisa has the lowest percentage of 11, while 16% of the respondents answered Digman Halo-halo.

Figure 3: Presents data that refers to which of the following had increased the awareness of the participants in regards with the cuisines

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Social media	50	35.5%
Family/relatives	68	48.2%
Peers/friends	23	16.3%

Data presented through family and relatives is the majority of where the respondents have heard the mentioned cuisines, with a percentage of 48.2, followed by the answer: social media, with a total percentage of 35.5, and finally, 16.3% of the respondents answered peer/friends.

Table 2: Presents the Familiarity level: Legacy cuisines of Cavite

No.	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	Digman halo-halo	3.73	Familiar
2	Imus longganisa	3.69	Familiar
3	Bacalao	2.68	Somewhat familiar
4	Pipian	2.69	Somewhat familiar

Table shows that Digman Halo-halo and Imus longganisa are both familiar to the study participants, and Bacalao and Pipian are neutral or somewhat familiar to the respondents.

Table 3: Familiarity level in terms of accessibility: where can the cuisines be purchased

No.	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	Digman halo-halo	3.53	Familiar
2	Imus longganisa	3.51	Familiar
3	Bacalao	2.59	Unfamiliar
4	Pipian	2.57	Unfamiliar

Table shows that the study participants know where to find or purchase the Digman Halo-halo and Imus longganisa. At the same time, the Bacalao and Pipian are mostly unfamiliar to the respondents, which means that they are also unfamiliar with where to find the cuisine or where it could be purchased.

Table 4: Presents data that determines the awareness level of the participants about the Cavite's cuisines

No.	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	Digman halo-halo	3.73	Aware
2	Imus longganisa	3.62	Aware
3	Bacalao	2.7	Unaware
4	Pipian	2.66	Neither aware or unaware

Based on the data gathered, participants know that the Digman Halo-halo and Imus longganisa are a legacy cuisine of Cavite, and they are unaware that the Bacalao is a legacy of Cavite. However, the Pipian is neutral or neither aware nor unaware of the subject; it is a legacy cuisine of Cavite.

Table 8: Insights towards preserving the legacy cuisines of Cavite

No.	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	These cuisines are a reflection of the cultural background of Cavite and so, could be preserved through either of: the original methods of how to make the cuisines must be preserved without any changes or these cuisines could be made with changes or adjustments from the original methods.	4.03	Agree

From the data gathered, participants have agreed that the mentioned cuisines of Cavite are to be preserved with two possible techniques or strategies: keep the original method of making the cuisine and follow the procedure without any changes or make adjustments or changes on how to make the cuisine.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The legacy of Cavite's cuisines is effectively promoted.

Regarding where the participants have heard a particular cuisine among the four mentioned cuisines, it is

the majority that family and relatives increased their awareness. Social media is the second highest percentage, and the least is peers/friends. However, six aspects and factors have been mentioned that establish information on what affects a consumer's decision-making when trying food or cuisine: price, quality, food appearance, trend, familiarity, and accessibility. So, it still applies to what could be a tool to increase the number of people curious about Digman Halo-halo, Imus longganisa, Bacalao, and Pipian.

2. The significance of the study

The study obtained information about Digman halo-halo, Imus longganisa Bacalao, and Pipian, which is a way to boost the reader's curiosity and might eventually result in an increased number of people who could recognize the mentioned cuisine. When recognition is achieved, reviving is as follows to be interpreted as achieved, and so, achieving the two goals, such as recognizing and reviving, promotion is also exhibited.

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